

Psychological Factors Influencing Men's Participation in Family planning In Kakamega County, Kenya

Mildred Lumayo^{1*}

¹Department of Sociology, Gender and Development Studies, Kisii University, Kisii, Kenya

*Corresponding author email: lumayomildred@kisiiversity.ac.ke

Published online: 5th July, 2023

Abstract

Family planning has attracted attention all over the world due to its relevance in decision making, population growth and development. The purpose of this paper was to investigate the psychological factors influencing men's participation in family planning practices in Kakamega County, Kenya. This study adopted cross-sectional survey design using mixed methodology. The study targeted a total of 17469 household heads in Likuyani, Malava and Lugari Sub-Counties. Sample size determination formula was used to obtain 376 respondents. Stratified, simple random, purposive and systematic random sampling techniques were used to select the participants. Questionnaires, interviews and document analysis were used to collect data. Instrument validity was done through expert judgement while reliability involved the use of the test-retest method. Data obtained was analyzed using quantitative and qualitative techniques. Frequencies and percentages were used to analyze quantitative data. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine the relationship that existed between the independent variables and dependent variables. Qualitative data from interview schedules were transcribed, thematically classified and arranged before they were finally reported in narrations and quotations. The study found a significant negative correlation between psychological factors and men's participation in family planning in Kakamega County ($r = -.286$; $p = .000$). This shows that psychological factors affect men's participation in family planning practices in Kakamega county. The study recommended that promotion and sensitization campaigns on various family planning methods and their advantages, mainly targeting men, need to be undertaken in the region by the national government, county government and non-state actors. This study may be of importance to couples in understanding the psychological factors that hinder men in participating in family planning practices. In addition, by understanding the psychological factors affecting family planning, the government and other healthcare partners in Kenya may use the findings in providing health education on family planning.

Key words: Psychological Factors, Influencing, Men, Participation Family planning

1.0 Introduction

The importance of family planning practice by women and men cannot be underrated today. Sub-Saharan Africa faces a myriad of challenges relating to poor pregnancy outcomes, unwanted pregnancies and generally challenges emanating from the high cost of living in households. These challenges can be reduced and even done away with if both women and men together join in family planning practice. Conventionally, family planning programmes have been focused on females and this is attributed to the fact that it is females who become expectant and thus are faced with the health dangers related to pregnancies and deliveries and therefore, have apparently the highest motivation to avert unplanned pregnancies (Kaida, Walter, Hessel & Konde-Lule, 2004). Furthermore, females are more expected to be much in contact with the healthcare system due to their general obligation for family health, particularly for the health and wellbeing of babies and siblings under five years of age. However, involving males in family planning (FP) practices has been shown to directly affect the sexual partner's fertility health selections, behaviours and decision-making process (Soremekun, 2014).

Family planning is very vital and especially in the contemporary world which is faced by quite a number of challenges (Mbizvo, & Phillips, 2014). These challenges include poverty, diseases, ignorance and a high population with the high costs of living which leads to high crime rates, food insecurity, development of slums and poor health conditions for the many children born day and night. The process of reproduction encompasses both men and women and although the array of contraceptives involves strategies, namely vasectomy, condoms and withdrawal that males utilize unswervingly and the Standard Days Method (SDM) that necessitates their involvement, females are still the main targets for family planning (Melanie & Gay, 2017). Family planning (FP) 2020's objective categorically aims at reaching an additional 120 million girls and women with family planning methods. Boender *et al.*, as cited in Prata *et al.*, (2017) pointed out that at the 1994 International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) in Cairo, that a renewed call to engage males more aggressively in reproductive health was arrived at. The framing of ICPD stressed males as partners in supporting the autonomous choices of females, however, there was less emphasis with regard to male's fertility, health and rights (Wentzell, & Inhorn, 2014).

Family planning practices are vital in promoting the decrease in maternal and newborn mortality rates. Enhancing the accessibility of family planning programmes and services and

working up on utilisation of family planning services particularly in less developed nations would prevent up to 42% of maternal mortalities (Shazia, *et al.*, 2010). Additionally, the world reproduction report pointed out that the use of family planning techniques differed widely from 69% in South-East Asia to 11% in Africa (Darroch *et al.*, 2013). It is apparent that the extensive implementation of family planning practices characterizes one of the most dramatic variations of the 20th century. The growing adoption of contraceptive use around the world has given married people the opportunity of selecting the number and spacing of their siblings, which, further, has averted a large number of unwanted pregnancies and their implications. Despite these inspiring gains, contraceptive use and implementation is still very low and therefore, high provision of contraceptives is still needed in the world's poorest countries (PRB, 2012). Evidence from UNFPA, (2012), points out that there are high unmet needs for contraceptive use and implementation in most developing countries and is even considered higher in Sub-Saharan nations where some females with unmet need for contemporary contraceptives increased from 31 million in the year 2008 to 36 million in 2012.

Evaluation of contraception programming for males underpins that males need extra contraceptive choices outside the strategies that are currently accessible to them. Similarly, there is a high call for innovative men contraceptive choices especially for the rescindable contraception strategies (Glasier, 2010). In a survey by Heineman (2005) of more than 9,000 males of ages 18–59 and across nine countries, it emerged that 28.5 -- 71.4% of males of different nationalities articulated the preparedness of using hormonal male contraceptives. Moreover, in a study by Dorman and Bishai (2012) it emerged that despite the 25% of males who were willing to use male contraception in the Heinemann *et al.*, (2005) study, it was projected that the number of possible users of ages 15–64 years in the specific nations was close to 44 million. Studies of female's satisfactoriness of a male pill use in Edinburgh, Cape Town, Shanghai and Hong Kong indicated that while female partners did not have trust on males in general, they were more trusting when it came to their own partner (Glasier, 2010). In a similar study in south-west Nigeria involving 329 males of varied ages ranging from 18 – 60 years and who were either married or cohabiting and had at least one child, it emerged that majority of males were willing to undergo reversible male contraception (Olayinka, Okafor & Odugbemi 2016). However, a study by Baker *et al.*, (2011) in Malawi found that men believed that the best family planning strategies were those meant for females and therefore, males were deemed not to be using any contraception.

The barrier to male engagement in family planning practices is deemed to differ across various countries due to differences in customary beliefs and traditions. Outstandingly, the acknowledged barriers to men participation included financial difficulties (9.3%) and insufficient information on FP strategies (8.2%). This finding is similar to those found in Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) Ghana and Ethiopia (Adongo, Tapsoba & Phillips 2013; Ditekemena, Koole & Engmann, 2012). Some of the contemporary female FP strategies discourage males from being engaged. Similarly, since some males are uninformed or do not have acceptable information on FP, their engagement is affected to the same extent. Some respondents in the study reported that they were not engaged in FP since their customs and traditions did not permit them to participate. They claimed that in their culture, Family Planning was considered to be a women's activity and so they did not see any reasons as to why they should be involved in the practice. Also, their fondness for large family sizes made it challenging for them to support any strategies that went against such interests.

A study by Jalang'o, Thuita, Barasa, and Njoroge (2017) in Kenya found out that religious attachment was closely related to the utilisation of family planning methods. The study revealed that people affiliated to Seventh Day Adventist churches had more likelihood of adopting family planning practices. Females who ascribed to Seventh Day Adventist acknowledged that they were being trained on family planning practices in church to permit them to plan the time of having their siblings.

The effectiveness of family planning methods has been considered by researchers to be highly dependent on user characteristics such as education level (Alemayehu, & Abebach, 2014; family Health International, 2007). It has been observed that females with higher education status were more likely to adopt a family planning method in Ethiopia (Okech, Wawire, & Mburu, (2011). Furthermore, Wachira (2001), in a study on contraception in Kenya reveals that women with secondary education and above had a higher level of contraceptive use than higher education. These studies reveal that the level of education affects the use of family planning methods.

MacQuarrie, (2014) pointed out that in Tanzania an analysis of DHS data revealed unmet need for family planning to be highest amongst young married women with no children than those with a child. This shows that married women consider using various family planning methods as a way of spacing their children or avoiding unwanted pregnancies. This is attributed to the fact that young unmarried people may have less frequent sexual relations than married people (Sedekia *et al.*, 2017).

The complex nature of the environments in which third world countries operate in affects to a large extent the use of contraceptives. Therefore, even though the topic on contraceptives have been examined previously by a number of scholars, the challenges pertaining to contraceptive use are yet to be dealt with. Contraceptive use is presumed to be influenced by many psychosocial factors. Some of these factors include; education, place of residence, employment status, marital status, religion, ethnicity, region of residence, knowledge of method and knowledge of source of method. Thus, the current study investigated the psychological factors influencing men’s participation in family planning in Kakamega County, Kenya

2.0 Research Methodology

A cross-sectional survey design was adopted for this study. This made it possible to rapidly collect data from a large sample within the shortest time possible by use of questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis. Additionally, the study adopted a convergent mixed methodology.

The research targeted three sub-counties; Malava (purely homogenous), Lugari (fairly mixed) and Likuyani purely (cosmopolitan in nature) with a total household population of 17,469 units. In each sub-county, data collection was narrowed down to two wards based on population density; one with the highest population density and one with the lowest population density. Further, the study targeted 93 public health officers who were in-charge of family planning units in the three sub-counties.

The sample size formula for this study was based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970) as quoted by Kasomo (2001). Using the formula, 376 households were selected to participate in the study. The sample size as per each ward is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample size per Wards in Likuyani Sub-County

Sub-County	Ward Name	Number of Households	Sample Size
Likuyani	Likuyani	3223	69
	Sinoko	2698	58
Malava	Butali/Chegulo	3584	77
	East Kabararas	2802	60
Lugari	Mautuma	2678	58
	Chekalini	2484	54
Total		17469	376

In order to ensure that representative samples are derived from each ward, a multi-stage-cum-stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting the household heads for the study. In the study, simple random sampling technique was used to select the first household in each ward followed by systematic random sampling where every 10th household was selected. The household heads present at the time of the study was issued with a questionnaire. This procedure ensured that all the members of the population are given an equal chance of being included in the sample. In selecting health care workers who are in-charge of family planning units, purposive sampling was used since there are six government healthcare centres in the region with 8 personnel manning the family planning units.

Questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from household heads while interviews were used to collect qualitative data from healthcare workers in-charge of family planning units in the various health centres. These instruments were piloted to a selected sample of household heads in the nearby Lugari sub-county which shares the same characteristics as Likuyani Sub-County. The researcher sought opinions from lecturers on content and construct validity. Comments solicited from them were used to improve the research instrument before commencing data collection. Foxcroft (2004), note that by using a panel of experts to review the test specifications and the selection of items, the content validity of a test can be improved. Test-retest method was employed to test the reliability of questionnaires. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (r) was used to calculate the reliability coefficient between the first and second scores. A correlation coefficient of 0.81 was obtained showing that the instruments were reliable and therefore adopted for use in the study.

Data obtained was analyzed using quantitative and qualitative techniques. The quantitative data from the questionnaires were first subjected to preliminary processing through validation, coding and tabulation in readiness for analysis with the help of the statistical package for social science (SPSS version 20) computer package as a 'toolbox' to analyze data related to objectives. Frequencies, percentages, mean and Standard deviation were used to analyze quantitative data. Qualitative data from interview schedules was transcribed, thematically classified and arranged before they were reported in narrations and quotations.

3.0 Results and Discussions

Studies have shown that there exist widespread myths and misconceptions about family planning methods for men. This study investigated the psychological factors influencing

men's participation in family planning in Kakamega County. Table 2 presents responses on psychological factors influencing men's participation in family planning practices as a development aspect.

Table 2: Psychological Factors Influencing Men's Participation in Family planning

Statement	SD		D		UD		A		SA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Ancestral customs in our society give men rights over women's procreative power in family planning issues	61	17.6	69	19.9	17	4.9	102	29.5	97	28.0
Perceived Side effects of use of family planning methods hinder men's involvement	46	13.3	30	8.7	13	3.8	191	55.2	66	19.1
Men who engage in Extra marital affairs frequently use FP methods	104	30.1	6	1.7	2	.6	121	35.0	113	32.7
FP methods Interferes with sexual pleasures	53	15.3	59	17.1	0	0.0	112	32.4	122	35.3

Source (Field Data, 2017)

Table 2 shows that 102(29.5%) respondents agreed with the statement that ancestral customs in their society gave men rights over women's procreative power in family planning issues, 97(28.0%) participants were strongly in agreement with the statement, 69(19.9%) participants were in disagreement and 61(17.6%) respondents strongly disagreed with the statement while 17(4.9%) respondents were neutral on the statement. The responses showed that the majority (57.5%) believed that ancestral customs gave men rights over women's procreative power in the family. This implies that decisions concerning family planning are mostly undertaken by men due to their cultural beliefs. This contradicts the research findings of Mansour *et al.*, (2016) who found out in their study that social and cultural norms did not influence men's decisions about family planning. However, the current study findings concur with those of other researchers including Babalola & Fatusi (2009), Filippi (2007) and Hogan (2010) who found out in their studies that men were exerting their power and not sharing decisions with their wives about the use and selection of family planning.

Similarly, 191(55.2%) study participants agreed with the statement that perceived side effects of use of family planning methods hinder men's involvement, 66(19.1%) respondents

strongly agreed with the statement, 46(13.3%) respondents strongly disagreed with the statement and 30(8.7%) respondents disagreed with the statement while 13(3.8%) respondents were undecided. The responses showed that the majority (74.3%) of the respondents believed that the perceived side effects associated with the utilization of family planning strategies hindered men's involvement in Kakamega County. This implies that there is a misconception on perceived side effects of utilisation of family planning strategies among the inhabitants of Kakamega County therefore hindering the effective family planning practices. This study finding is found to be similar to those of Tibaijuka *et al.*, (2017) who found in their study that Side effects seemed to influence stoppage of family planning use rather than method selection. Further, the finding supported those of Jay, *et al.*, (2017) who found in their study that the most common reason women choose not to use contraceptives was the side effects believed to be associated with contraceptives.

Additionally, 121(35.0%) respondents agreed with the statement that men who engage in extra marital affairs frequently use FP methods, 113(32.7%) respondents strongly agreed with the statement while 110(31.8%) respondents were in disagreement with the statement. As shown by the responses, it seems that the majority (67.7%) of the respondents believed that men who engage in extra marital affairs frequently used FP methods. This implies that men who engage in extra marital affairs use family planning methods as a way of preventing sexually transmitted diseases and unwanted pregnancies outside marriage. This supports an earlier finding of Oyedokun, (2007) who found that in Nigeria, men believed that if their wives used any of the modern methods, she had engaged in extra-marital affairs.

Further, 122(35.3%) of the study participants were strongly in agreement with the statement that FP methods interferes with sexual pleasures, 112(32.4%) respondents agreed with the statement and 59(17.1%) respondents disagreed with the statement while 53(15.3%) respondents strongly disagreed with the statement. The study found out that majority (67.7%) of the respondents believed that use of family planning methods interfered with sexual pleasures. This is consistent with the findings of other researchers including UmohAbah and Ekanem (2012).

On interviewing the healthcare facility in-charges, it emerged that males were psychologically not prepared to use contemporary strategies of family planning. One of the facility in-charges pointed out that;

Use of modern methods of family planning like vasectomy cannot easily be accepted in this area since it psychologically tortures men. Men cannot imagine undergoing vasectomy (A 37-year Clinical Officer, Milimani health Centre, 2017).

3.1 Relationship between Psychological Factors and Men’s Participation in Family Planning Practices as a Development Aspect

The hypothesis of this study stated that:

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between psychological factors and men’s participation in family planning Practises as a development aspect.

This hypothesis was also tested using Pearson Correlation Coefficient analysis. The results of the analyzed data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation Coefficient between Psychological factors and Men’s Participation in Family Planning

	Men’s Participation in Family Planning
Psychological factors	r = -.286** p = .000 n = 346

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that there was a weak and negative correlation between psychological factors and men’s participation in family planning practices as a development aspect in Kakamega County (r = -.286; p = .000). This shows that at 95% confidence level, the r value for psychological factors was .286 showing a weak correlation with male’s involvement in family planning. The negative values show a negative correlation meaning that increased psychological factors lead to reduced male’s participation in family planning. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between psychological factors and males’ participation in family planning Practises as a development aspect was rejected. Hence there exists a significant relationship between psychological factors and men’s participation in family planning. However, this was a negative correlation showing a negative relationship, implying that increased psychological factors lead to decreased participation of males in family planning.

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study found a weak and negative correlation between psychological factors and men’s participation in family planning practices as a development aspect in Kakamega County.

Therefore, there exists a significant relationship between psychological factors such as perceived side effects of family planning methods and men's participation in family planning practices as a development aspect. However, this was a negative correlation showing a negative relationship; implying that increased psychological factors lead to decreased participation of men in family planning. Moreover, there was significant and positive correlation between socio-cultural factors such as cultural beliefs among men and men's participation in family planning showing that socio-cultural factors influence men's participation in family planning practices as a development aspect.

5.0 References

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